

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING GROUP WORK IN TEACHING WRITING SKILL FOR ENGLISH – MAJOR STUDENTS IN HUFU

Dang Thi Hong Nhung

Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry

Email: nhungdang339@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Effective writing skill is central in both university education and in the world of work that follows. Writing well is a major challenge, because it is at once a test of memory, language, and thinking ability. One must have the capacity to maintain multiple representations and control interactions among planning, generation, and reviewing in order to write well. At Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry, writing is a big challenge for many English - major students who rarely have chances to practice writing at high schools. The students have many troubles with their grammar, ideas and other problems, which makes the teaching of writing become a difficulty for the teachers. The study is intended to examine the students' problems and evaluate the effectiveness of using group work to help students overcome their own challenges and improve their writing skill.

Key words: group work, writing skill, challenges, effectiveness

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

English is the international language. It's a necessary language to enable community to involve in global communication. Students need to be able to master four English skills: speaking, listening, reading and writing. According to Brown (2004:218) writing is the skill that is the exclusive domain of scribes and scholars in educational and religious institutions. Writing is especially important for students as they can express their ideas and experiences in written form. However, most students realize that the learning to write fluently and correctly is difficult. It is because writing needs the control of many variables. As Zemach and Islam (2004:12) stated that there are some aspects included in writing such as control of content, rules of syntax, format sentence, grammar, punctuation, vocabulary and spelling. Unfortunately, the students' ability in writing is still far from what is being expected. Many of them can not write correctly grammatical sentences due to their limited vocabulary and ideas, their mistakes with punctuation and spelling.

One technique that can solve the problem is using group work. Group work or collaborative has become a well – known and widespread activity in most English as a foreign language (EFL) and English as a second language (ESL) writing classes. Group work refers to students working together in small groups on specific activities with everyone being required to participate actively (Cohen, 1994). Many benefits have been claimed for group work. One of them is that it can help

weak students to learn more effectively when they work with strong partners. Moreover, it enables students to acquire and develop various skills such as leadership, thinking, motivating and encouraging low – motivated students (D. Johnson & Ahlgren , 1976).

Group work in the context of writing means two or more students working together to produce and complete a writing text through practicing stages and activities such as collecting, planning and organizing ideas, drafting, revising and editing (Rice & Huguley, 1994).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Having taught writing skills for first - year and second – year students majoring in English in Ho Chi Minh City, University of Food Industry (HUFI), the present researcher noticed that the students were not reaching the intended writing assessment goals by the end of the course. Students are required to write paragraphs and essays both in class and in final exams. Their writing products are marked and judged by their teachers on the basis of format, content, unity and coherence, grammar, word usage and mechanism.

After two years of teaching the students, the researcher has observed and identified certain problems. It's a common problem that the students lack of ideas and vocabulary which affects on the content of the writing. They also have difficulties with grammar, word choice and format. Some of the students even make spelling mistakes.

1.3 Aims of the study

The aim of this study is to investigate the usefulness of using group work on the process of teaching writing skill to the English – majored students in HUFI. In other words, *it* seeks the answer to the following question:

“Would using group work in teaching writing skill be more effective than traditional approach as individual work?”

1.4 Methodology

The study was conducted in accordance with the observation approach. The researcher observed students working in groups in writing class.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The process of writing

According to Raimes, 1985 the process of writing consists of 3 stages: the pre – writing stage, the while – writing stage, the post – writing stage. Different tasks are conducted in different stages; therefore, students have to be taught writing through stages and tasks such as planning, drafting, revising, editing and publishing in order to have writing products of good quality.

2.2 Pre – writing stage

An essential feature of writing is that students collect and produce ideas. Brainstorming and discussions are helpful strategies that may be used to collect and gather ideas effectively

(Hewings and Curly, 2003). Brainstorming means thinking quickly and in order to produce idea to a specific problem. Planning a topic is also an important strategy in pre – writing stage that helps learners to organize the writing successfully. Another pre – writing technique is making notes to generate ideas. Organizing ideas is a structuring strategy that could be carried out through selecting appropriate names as headings and categories (White & Arndt, 1991). Making an outline during the pre – writing stage is another good strategy. Writers may find it necessary and useful to write down their important ideas in outline forms, starting with small ideas and moving to general ideas.

2.3 While – writing stage

While – writing stage comes after the completion of pre – writing activities. In this stage, writers start their first draft which they should keep writing from beginning to end without stopping (Gebhard, 2000). According to King and Chapman (2003), during this stage writers should focus on the actual writing and leave the grammatical and spelling stage to the final stage.

2.4 Post – writing stage

The main concern of post – writing stage is to complete the content correctly and correcting grammatical and spelling mistakes. Focusing on reorganizing sentences and adding more appropriate vocabulary are essential aspects of post – writing stage (William, 2003). This stage also concentrates on linguistic accuracy: grammar, spelling, punctuation.

3 METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, the current situation of teaching and learning writing skill of English - majored students is described as the setting for the study. The data gathered from the questionnaire discussed in terms of their purposes and how they are exploited in the study.

3.1. Research context

The study was conducted at Ho Chi Minh City, University of Food Industry which is one of the Universities in the south of Vietnam.

The teaching of English at HUFU is divided into two phases. In the first phase, students study general English with four skills: writing, listening, reading and speaking. One teacher is responsible for teaching writing skill during the whole semester for one class. In the second phase, students study Business English and related subjects to this major.

The students have one writing lesson every week in 15 weeks with two periods for each lesson (each period is 45 minutes long).

3.2 Research questions

The study has been conducted to answer two research questions: Would using group work in teaching writing skill be more effective than traditional approach as individual work?

3.3 Research approach

The study was conducted in accordance with the observation and interview approach. That is because the study focused on the attitude of students when they work in group in writing class. The data was collected from the researchers' observation in writing classes in HUFU. The data was also collected from the answers for interview questions.

3.4 Data Collection Instrument

In this investigation, the researcher acted as an observer. The researcher observed the activities of students in order to know the effectiveness of using group work in writing lessons. Besides, students were asked to answer interview questions and questionnaire about their attitudes towards group work in a writing class and perceptions of group work. The questionnaire was divided into two sections: section 1 was concerned with the attitudes and perceptions of students regarding writing skills; section 2 was concerned with group work. In both section of the questionnaire, different levels of agreement were stated from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree". The students were asked to choose one of five responses (strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, strongly disagree) for each of the question. During the analysis of the questionnaire data, the answers were assigned a number for the purpose of scoring: e.g., "strongly agree" = 1, "agree" = 2 and so on.

4 FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The purpose of the study is to determine whether using group work in teach writing skill is useful or not. The results obtained from the observation and the interview leads to some analysis and recommendations.

4.1 Findings

4.1.1 Finding about attitudes of students towards writing skills

The first questionnaire aimed at collecting general information about writing skills. It's important to acquire background information about the students' attitude towards writing in general before asking them the perception of group work. The results of the first questionnaire was described in the table below.

N	QUESTIONS	1	2	3	4	5
1	Writing is difficult for me.	63%	24%	6%	7%	0%
2	Writing isn't just completing a composition, but planning, drafting, revising and editing.	57%	15%	10%	5%	3%
3	Before starting writing, I spend a lot of time trying to understand the topic.	25%	37%	15%	15%	7%
4	I often have difficulties understanding the topic of the tasks.	21%	24%	13%	30%	12%

N	QUESTIONS	1	2	3	4	5
5	Before starting, I usually write down ideas and make outline.	13%	17%	11%	39%	20%
6	It's difficult for me to get ideas for my writing topic.	38%	31%	10%	17%	5%
7	During the writing stage, I usually follow the plan that I have written before starting to write.	9%	14%	12%	42%	23%
8	During the writing stage, I concentrate on using the vocabularies supplied by my teacher.	46%	31%	3%	12%	8%
9	During the editing stage, I have difficulties to find appropriate words and vocabularies for the mistakes.	43%	35%	6%	10%	6%
10	During the editing stage, I have difficulties in correcting grammar and spelling mistakes.	39%	30%	4%	19%	8%

It can be clearly seen that the high percentage of students had difficulties with writing and how to start their writing. Many of them had trouble with brainstorming ideas and vocabularies for the tasks. The majority of the students depended much on their teachers in providing necessary vocabularies and words. Only a small percentage of them tried to understand the task carefully and prepare for the tasks before starting to write. However, while the students were writing, fewer of them used the ideas that they had planned beforehand. In the post – writing stage, most of the students had challenges with correcting their own mistakes. They even hardly identified their mistakes in terms of word usage, grammatical and spelling errors.

4.1.2 Findings about students' attitude towards group work

N	QUESTIONS	1	2	3	4	5
1	Working together in groups is a good strategy that helps me write effectively.	48%	31%	5%	12%	5%
2	Working by myself without help from others is more effective for me.	5%	7%	12%	46%	30%
3	Before starting to write (pre – writing stage), planning outlines with friends is much better than individually.	30%	51%	4%	8%	7%
4	Before starting to write (pre – writing stage), making an outline and writing down ideas with friends are not useful.	2%	7%	13%	35%	33%
5	At the pre – writing stage, talking with my friends can help me facilitate ideas and vocabularies for the writing task.	38%	36%	7%	10%	9%

N	QUESTIONS	1	2	3	4	5
6	During the writing stage, I often use the ideas, vocabularies and outlines which I gain from group work.	36%	41%	8%	9%	6%
7	During the writing stage, I hardly use the ideas, vocabularies and outlines which I gain from group work.	11%	13%	6%	39%	31%
8	During the editing stage, working in groups helps me much in correcting my mistakes and improving my compositions.	36%	38%	10%	9%	8%
9	During the editing stage, I can correct my mistakes and improve my compositions without help from others.	13%	10%	7%	40%	30%
10	Reading my group mates' compositions and sharing my compositions with them is useful and beneficial.	46%	37%	7%	8%	5%

Looking at the data, it can be concluded that the students' attitude towards group work was quite positive. The majority of them agreed that group work in a writing class have helped them overcome their problems that they had when they worked individually. At the pre – writing stage, group work supplied the students a wide variety of ideas and vocabularies when they worked with their group. This also helped the students understand the task more clearly. Thanks to making the outlines with their group mates, many students could be able to apply what they gained to their compositions in while – writing process. At the editing stage, a high percentage of students agreed and strongly agreed that the help from their peers was useful. In other words, they found that editing and revising their compositions as well as correcting the mistakes with others helped them improve their essays much better.

4.2 Recommendations

4.2.1 Pre – writing stage

By the end of the course, it can be realized that students in the control group felt that they have started to spend longer time understanding the writing task and the writing topic before becoming involved in the writing thanks to group work. Therefore, it's recommended to use group work with different activities at this stage in teaching writing skills. The activities may vary depending on the topic and the class context. During this stage, students had better have time to discuss the task requirement, brainstorm ideas and exchange ideas together to choose the best ones. They can also help each other by discussing about the organization of their writing which may be the challenge for some students. When working in group, many students overcome their first troubles such as lack of ideas or misunderstanding of topics.

4.2.2 While – writing stage

While – writing stage, in fact is a period of individual work. However, it is still beneficial to students when they have chance to work in group in pre – writing stage. After gaining ideas and certain vocabularies in the previous stage with their partners, it was easier for students to get started with their writing. Students also confirmed that they had fewer difficulties with the organization of the writing as they had discussed with others beforehand. As a result, they could do their writing more smoothly and attentively.

4.2.3 Post – writing stage

After having the first draft, group work once again is very useful for learners. At this stage, the students worked in groups to help each other correct grammatical and spelling mistakes. All the students in control group agreed that group work during the revising and editing stage was used to solve difficulties. As a matter of fact, the students claimed that it had been hard for them to identify their own mistakes. However, when they worked in group, they could find out their partners' mistakes more easily. Consequently, the students believed that during post – writing stage, group work was beneficial for their writing.

4 CONCLUSION

This research has investigated the usefulness of using group work in teach writing skill for English – majored students in HUFU. This model was found useful and effective in teaching and learning writing. The results showed that group work was beneficial for control group in all three stages: pre – writing stage, while – writing stage and post – writing stage. The attitude and perception of the students toward writing had also developed in positive trends.

REFERENCES

- [1] Gebhard, J. (2000). *Teaching English as a Foreign or Second Language*, The University of Michigan Press.
- [2] Hewings, A & Curry, M. (2003) *Teaching academic writing: A toolkit for higher education*, Routledge, London and New York.
- [3] King, R & Chapman, C. (2003) *Differentiated instructional strategies for writing in the content areas*, Corwin Press, INC.
- [4] Raimes, A. (1985) *What unskilled ESL do as they write: A classroom study of Composing*, TESOL Quarterly, 19 (2), 229 – 258.
- [5] White, R.V. & Arndt, V. (1991) *Process Writing*, London: Longman.
- [6] William, J. (2003) *Preparing to teach writing: Research, theory and practice*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Third Edition.

APPENDIX 1: QUESTIONNAIRE TO COLLECT STUDENTS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS WRITING

1. Strongly Agree
2. Agree
3. Undecided
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree

N	QUESTIONS	1	2	3	4	5
1	Writing is difficult for me.					
2	Writing isn't just completing a composition, but planning, drafting, revising and editing.					
3	Before starting writing, I spend a lot of time trying to understand the topic.					
4	I often have difficulties understanding the topic of the tasks.					
5	Before starting, I usually write down ideas and make outline.					
6	It's difficult for me to get ideas for my writing topic.					
7	During the writing stage, I usually follow the plan that I have written before starting to write.					
8	During the writing stage, I concentrate on using the vocabularies supplied by my teacher.					
9	During the editing stage, I have difficulties to find appropriate words and vocabularies for the mistakes.					
10	During the editing stage, I have difficulties in correcting grammar and spelling mistakes.					

APPENDIX 2: QUESTIONNAIRE TO COLLECT STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS GROUP WORK

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Undecided
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree

N	QUESTIONS	1	2	3	4	5
1	Working together in groups is a good strategy that helps me write effectively.					
2	Working by myself without help from others is more effective for me.					
3	Before starting to write (pre – writing stage), planning a topic with friends is much better than individually.					
4	Before starting to write (pre – writing stage), making an outline and writing down ideas with friends are not useful.					
5	At the pre – writing stage, talking with my friends can help me facilitate ideas and vocabularies for the writing task.					
6	During the writing stage, I often use the ideas, vocabularies and outlines which I gain from group work.					
7	During the writing stage, I hardly use the ideas, vocabularies and outlines which I gain from group work.					
8	During the editing stage, working in groups helps me much in correcting my mistakes and improving my compositions.					
9	During the editing stage, I can correct my mistakes and improve my compositions without help from others.					
10	Reading my group mates' compositions and sharing my compositions with them is useful and beneficial.					